

THE IMPORTANCE OF PERSONALISED EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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***Annotation.** In this article, the theoretical foundations, essence, advantages, and effectiveness of learner-centered educational technology in the process of upbringing are discussed. In addition, the pedagogical and psychological significance of the learner-centered approach, its role in the development of the learner's personality, and its impact on the effectiveness of upbringing are scientifically analyzed.*

***Keywords:** upbringing process, learner-centered education, pedagogical technology, individualization, humanism, educator, social competence.*

In today's era of globalization, improving the education system on the basis of humanity, democracy and innovation is one of the urgent issues. Person-centered educational technology places the student or trainee at the center of the educational process, and involves developing them taking into account their needs, interests and individual capabilities. The use of this technology in the educational process is of great importance in the formation of independent thinking, social activity and moral qualities of the individual.

Therefore, the use of person-centered educational technologies in the modern educational process is one of the most important requirements of the educational system. Because today the educational process is not limited to providing knowledge, but also involves the comprehensive development of the student's personality, ensuring his social, moral and spiritual maturity. Person-centered education is a pedagogical approach that puts the student or pupil at the center of the educational process, taking into account his individual characteristics, abilities and interests. The importance of this technology in the educational process is incomparable. Because education is a continuous process that continues throughout a person's life, forming his spiritual, moral and social qualities.

Person-centered technologies in education are based on the principles of humanity, trust and mutual respect. Person-centered educational technology is a process of teaching and upbringing, organized in pedagogical activity taking into account the specific aspects of the student's personality. This technology serves to form the student's independent thinking, creativity, self-awareness and self-development skills.

While in the traditional education system the student is considered more as an object of knowledge, in person-centered education he becomes an active subject, that is, a full participant in the educational process. The teacher plays the role of a guide, advisor and encourager in this process. The uniqueness of the person-centered approach in the educational process is that it requires a deep study of the inner world, interests and needs of each student. The teacher educates students not in the same way, but in a way that suits their needs and abilities.

When working with students, the teacher takes into account their emotions, character and social experience, creating opportunities for their growth as individuals.

This process requires a high level of pedagogical skills, psychological sensitivity and communication culture from the educator. As F. Kadirova noted, the effectiveness of person-centered education depends on a positive psychological environment between the educator and the student. In this case, the student learns to freely express his opinion, justify his decisions and feel responsible for his actions.

In pedagogical literature (Yuldoshev J.G., Hasanboeva O., Abdukodirov A.), person-centered education is interpreted as an educational model based on humanistic ideas, expanding the possibilities of self-development of the student's personality. This approach requires the teacher not to control the student's activity, but to create conditions for it, direct and stimulate it.

Such technology is based on the principles of individualization, cooperation, reflection and activity. Namely:

- treating the individual with respect;
- listening to and taking into account the opinion of the student;
- establishing a dialogue based on cooperation and trust;
- recognizing and encouraging the success of each student.

As a result of personality-oriented education, students learn to freely express their opinions, feel responsible, and make independent decisions. The advantages of person-centered educational technology in the educational process can be summarized as follows:

1. It relies on individuality. It takes into account the abilities and capabilities of each student.
2. It increases motivation. The student feels his success, a positive attitude towards education is formed.
3. It develops creativity. Each person has the opportunity to independently express his opinion, create new ideas.
4. It increases social activity. The student finds his place in the team, learns to respect the opinions of others.
5. It strengthens moral education. In the educational process, human values, responsibility, honesty and solidarity are strengthened.

Thus, a person-centered approach transforms education from a one-sided process into an interactive, creative and humane system. In conclusion, it can be said that person-centered educational technology allows organizing the educational process in a modern, effective and humane direction. Through this technology, the teacher not only imparts knowledge, but also determines the path of personal development of each student, reveals his positive qualities. As a result, students are formed as independent thinkers, responsible, socially active and morally mature individuals. Thus, the use of person-centered educational technology in the educational process is the most important factor in raising mature, well-rounded people of the future society.

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